

Romanian language and literature interactive e-textbook: a case study of educational innovation

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Abstract: This article describes a case study of the interactive e-textbook of the Romanian Language and Literature for the 4th grade developed with the MDIRConstructor builder. This research focuses on the Moldovan experience regarding the development of interactive e-textbooks, within the national project “Development and implementation of interactive digital textbooks in pre-university education”. The study aims to extend the practice of developing interactive e-textbooks through the personalized approach and to increase the potential of digital textbooks through various educational resources.

Keywords: MDIRConstructor e-textbook builder; Interactive Digital Textbook, authentic digital teaching resources.

Rezumat: Articolul descrie un studiu de caz al manualului digital interactiv de limba și literatura română pentru clasa a IV-a dezvoltat cu ajutorul aplicației MDIRConstructor. Cercetarea elucidează experiența națională privind dezvoltarea manualelor digitale interactive, realizată în cadrul proiectului național de stat „Elaborarea și implementarea manualelor digitale interactive în învățământul preuniversitar”. Studiul își propune să extindă practica dezvoltării manualelor digitale interactive prin abordarea personalizată și să crească potențialul manualelor digitale prin implementarea diferitor tipuri de resurse educaționale.

Cuvinte-cheie: constructorul de manuale digitale MDIRConstructor; manuale digitale interactive, resurse digitale autentice.

1. INTRODUCTION

At present, the current government program of the Republic of Moldova declares digital transformation an imperative and strategic priority to ensure an innovative and inclusive digital society (*Strategia de transformare digitală a Republicii Moldova pentru anii 2023-2030*) [1]. The objectives of this transformation are to fit all societal sectors, including the educational system, which is going to mature as a proactive education system that supports digital transformation. As stated in the current and previous policies (*Strategia națională de dezvoltare a societății informaționale “Moldova Digitală 2020”*) [2], the transition of the educational system to a new, technological, and qualitative level and the use of digital didactic resources remain the most important goals in promoting digital knowledge and skills. We also mention that the National Programme in the fields of research and innovation of Moldova (2020-2023) [3], referring to the harnessing of human and social capital, aims to adapt the educational system to the alternative approaches in contemporary society. Following these strategic directions, we consider that one priority for the improvement of education in the Republic of Moldova is the digitalization of educational materials, whereas the variety of current editing tools and viewing devices affords the opportunity to implement them in an innovative educational environment.

A digital textbook is an excellent tool for organizing the learning environment, which could be managed both by the teacher and individually by the student. Also, it is a means of education, considered to be a more complex learning

tool, which helps the process of training or self-training of the students. Its combination with other ways, methods, or forms of learning can be related either to a system of lessons (or a chapter, or unit) or a lesson that, through specific sequences, serves the purpose of understanding, application, synthesis, analysis, or evaluation of knowledge.

The utilization of technology in the learning process, especially the use of electronic books, certainly has a major influence on the learning process stated Sari et al. [4]. M. Vlada (2014) described a digital textbook from its technical aspects and from the point of view of content [5]. Thus, according to the researcher, “the digital textbook represents a software product (application) that can be used online and offline on any type of technology (desktop, laptop, tablet, phone), it is independent of any operating systems and any browsers, and it is stored on a CD that comes with the printed manual. The content of a digital textbook includes the content of the printed textbook, having complementary specific elements such as interactive exercises, educational games, animations, movies, and simulations”.

Currently, a lot of countries worldwide use this learning resource in education, either as an interactive and collaborative digital educational means or as an auxiliary aid. Here, we would like to mention the experience of Romania in developing e-textbooks for all school disciplines and other didactic e-learning materials [6]. There are several Romanian publishers that elaborate digital textbooks for school disciplines, namely: *ART Digital*, *Corint*, *Litera Educational*, and *Intuitext*. For the current analysis, the digital textbooks of the Romanian language and literature in open access are

of particular interest, placed on the sites mentioned above. The identified publishers offer interactive learning resources for different school disciplines optimised with video, audio, edugames, interactive exercises, computer-assisted assessment, and others. Therefore, the Romanian digital textbook developers provide the transition from traditional paper information support to digital information support, establishing the promotion of the digitalization of education.

We note that in the Republic of Moldova, there is not any publisher that produces digital textbooks, hence, there is an acute need for this kind of learning material and such services. A couple of years ago, the national school textbooks were scanned and stored in pdf format on <https://mecc.gov.md/> and other administrative sites. These pdf textbooks are easily displayed on a computer screen or another device, but, in this case, we cannot speak on interactive digital learning means.

Teaching by traditional methods where there is only one way of communication is no longer sufficient. It is a demand of modern society to use information technologies in education according to multimedia and interactive features. They are developing rapidly in the last few years, influencing the process of converting traditional school textbooks into an interactive digital format. That's why the elaboration of interactive digital textbooks and auxiliaries persists as an urgent necessity for the education system of Moldova.

2. PURPOSE AND RESEARCH QUESTIONS

The main goal of this article is to analyse the practise of developing interactive e-textbooks through a personalised approach and to increase the potential of digital textbooks through various educational resources. On this basis, we present a case study of the interactive e-textbook of Romanian Language and Literature for the 4th grade. Speaking about "the personalised approach", the authors mean digital textbooks that incorporate learning materials for students created by teachers with an appropriate builder. Implementing digital textbooks in education is a vital factor in the digitalization of learning contexts. The general research questions of this study are: What tools serve to develop authentic teaching resources? How does an e-textbook

promote interactivity and original learning?

Through our research, we underline that digital textbooks should contain a set of various learning exercises and additional materials according to the specifics of one discipline in order to improve the students' involvement and motivation. The lack of free e-textbook builders on the software market determined us to develop an e-textbook builder called *MDIRConstructor* (author Nicolae Balmuş; registered by the State Agency of Intellectual Property of the Republic of Moldova, registration number 6765, 27.11.2020), which is promoted by the national project "Development and implementation of interactive digital textbooks in pre-university education". During the past two years, our research group has focused on the practise of the development of various interactive digital textbooks, including the elaboration of the Romanian Language and Literature for the 4th-grade e-textbook.

3. USAGE OF E-TEXTBOOK BUILDERS

In the case where interactive e-textbooks stand for digital versions of printed textbooks, proper tools are required to insert or develop various static and multimedia resources, interactive and self-evaluation exercises, simulations, games, and other types of resources. In addition, navigation, marking, search, zoom, selection, and other tools are suitable for providing the technical characteristics of an e-textbook.

3.1. e-Textbook builders' characteristics

To identify how to develop an interactive digital textbook, we examined several e-textbook builders, such as *Flip PDF* (commercial version), *Canva*, and *Visme Ebook Creator* (free versions). As a result, we found the commercial versions allowed more development opportunities compared to the free versions of some e-book creators.

We structure in Table 1 the following embedded interactive support properties of a digital textbook, considering one of the main goals of our research to develop genuine learning resources such as eduapplications, thematic software, websites that engage students in learning activities, practical exercises, comprehension exercises, and many others.

Table 1. *Embedded interactive support properties of a digital textbook*

Digital properties	Examples
Different types of digital resources	presentation, scheme, diagram, image, document, tutorials, dictionaries, web pages, printed word generated exercises, etc.
Multimedia	audio, video, simulations, recording and replaying voice files
Interactive excises	matching, true/false, multiple choice, grouping, crossword, ordering, and many others
Collaboration	annotation, document sharing, embedded shared links, discussion boards, mapping tools
Evaluation component	practice activities, embedded assessments
Easy access and friendly interface	the content of tables, selection, zoom, navigation, marking, search

the *MDIRConstructor* builder, we could design an interactive learning environment that integrates video, audio, images, and concept mind maps. Students can solve crosswords, match words and definitions, type the answer exercises, watch pictures, listen to audio clips, record their speech and conversation, hear spoken statements, link to a web video or page(s), share a document, use the *Note* tool to add notes or comments, and so on.

Figure 3. Example of the assessment task elaborated through the *Note* type of activities (text and audio sequence)

As noted, a digital textbook is an application that works autonomously on any computer or mobile device or in an online format and could incorporate interactive exercises, educational games, animations, movies, simulations, etc. That's why we strongly think the *MDIRConstructor* e-textbook builder is unique computer software that contributes to the training of teachers regarding the implementation of digital textbooks in the education system. Thus, in developing the prototype of the Romanian language and literature e-textbook, several types of educational resources were categorised as specific to this discipline. However, with the advancement of information technologies, more types of learning materials can be created that an e-textbook could provide.

CONCLUSION

The findings of the study reveal that the interactive digital textbook symbolises innovation and a renewed didactic model of a modern school, as well as an openness for the efficient implementation of learning contents. The goal of any e-context (either e-textbooks or stand-alone interactive exercises) is to assist the student in constructing the volume of knowledge necessary for further life activity. ICTs and digital textbooks represent extraordinary means of achieving a proper academic outcome. From this point of view, the procedure for creating digital textbooks must be in accordance with the curricula recommendations and respect the peculiarities of teaching activities, covering the entire range of actions, from design to content delivery in digital format. To expand the interest in implementing authentic digital textbooks and their usage in education, we conclude that one of the most important things is to own a digital textbook builder rich in tools that help create the most commonly used learning exercises. In this article, we also describe some interactive exercises implemented in the e-textbook of the Romanian language and literature for the 4th grade.

BIBLIOGRAPHICAL REFERENCES:

1. Strategia de transformare digitală a Republicii Moldova pentru anii 2023–2030 (STDM 2030). Concept. Pe: <https://particip.gov.md/ro/document/stages/proiectul-hotararii-guvernului-pentru-aprobarea-strategiei-de-transformare-digitala-a-republicii-moldova-pentru-anii-2023-2030/10429> (Accesat la 20.05.2023)
2. Strategia națională de dezvoltare a societății informaționale "Moldova Digitală 2020". Pe: <http://lex.justice.md/md/350246/> (Accesat la 25.05.2023)
3. Programul Național în domeniile cercetării și inovării pentru anii 2020–2023. Anexa nr.1 la Hotărârea Guvernului nr.381/2019. Pe: https://mecc.gov.md/sites/default/files/pnci_romana.pdf, (Accesat la 02.02.2023)
4. Sari S. et al. The importance of e-books in improving students' skills in physics learning in the 21st century: a literature review. *Journal of Physics: Conference Series* 2309, 2022. Pe: <https://iopscience.iop.org/article/10.1088/1742-6596/2309/1/012061/pdf> (Accesat la 09.06.2023)
5. Vlada, M. (2014), Ce este un manual digital? Pe: <https://www.elearning.ro/ce-este-un-manual-digital> (Accesat la 07.06.2023)
6. Ministerul Educației și Cercetării din România. Manuale școlare. Pe: <https://www.edu.ro/manuale-scolare> (Accesat la 03.11.2022)
7. Omar S. et al. Interactive language learning activities for learners' communicative ability. In: *International Journal of Evaluation and Research in Education (IJERE)*, Vol. 9, No. 4, 2020, pp. 1010-1016. Pe: <https://files.eric.ed.gov/fulltext/EJ1274774.pdf> (Accesat la 15.06.2023).